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Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

This data review examines the Survey on Persons Displaced from Ukraine. It was conducted in 2022 by the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. The survey focuses on the experiences of individuals, both adults and children, who fled Ukraine following Russia's 2022 full-scale invasion of Ukraine. The survey relied on a large, self-selected sample recruited through online channels across the following EU countries: Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Romania, Slovakia and Spain. The study's questionnaires cover a wide range of topics, including displacement histories, living conditions in a host country, family ties to those still residing in Ukraine, as well as access to rights and services for Ukrainians residing in the EU following February 2022. Access to the data is restricted and requires an approved application through GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences.

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Review of the Survey on Persons Displaced from Ukraine by Stas Gorelik

This dataset contains the results from the Survey on Persons Displaced from Ukraine, conducted in 2022 by the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, an independent body of the European Union. The survey examines the experiences of refugees who fled Ukraine following the Russia's full-scale invasion in February 2022 and subsequently settled in several countries of the European Union.

In particular, the survey covers those displaced persons who, at the time of the study, were residing in Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, and Spain. Individuals were eligible to be recruited in the sample if they had been living in Ukraine immediately before 24 February 2022 and had fled the country because of the onset of the war. Note that both Ukrainian citizens and individuals of other nationalities who had previously lived in Ukraine were surveyed.

The mode of data collection was CAWI, via a web link. Participation in the survey was voluntary and anonymous; moreover, respondents were asked to provide explicit consent for participation in the study. In terms of sampling, the study relied on open online recruitment (no probability sampling). A publicly accessible survey link that was widely disseminated by the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, as well as its partner organizations, including various NGO working with refugees. This was done across relevant websites and social media. The sample, therefore, represents a self-selected group of displaced persons from Ukraine. In total, 14,685 individuals took part in the survey (data being available in Stata and SPSS formats).

One of the survey's questionnaires was designed for adults (> 18 y/o), another targeted children and adolescents aged 12-17. Children aged 12-15 could participate in the study only after their parents or legal guardians had first completed the adult questionnaire and consented to their children's participation.

Substantively, the questionnaires cover several thematic areas related to displacement and integration: e.g., respondents' living arrangements before fleeing Ukraine and while residing in the host country (type of accommodation, participation in any domestic work in exchange for accommodation, rent payment conditions). Another set of questions focuses on whether respondents' family members remain in Ukraine and how frequently respondents stay in touch with those family members. Several questions concern the process of fleeing Ukraine and entering the European Union. Among other things, they ask about difficulties encountered when crossing the border with the European Union. The adult survey also examines respondents' access to rights and public services in the host country, including their understanding of what rights and benefits are actually available to them, such as education services (e.g., language course), employment opportunities, and housing assistance.

The children's questionnaire covers similar topics to those outlined above, but it was adapted accordingly to younger respondents. For instance, it asks about access to education and leisure activities, as well as children's own assessment of their well-being after displacement.

Access to the dataset is restricted. Researchers must submit a data use agreement describing their research project. After approval, the dataset will be distributed through GESIS – the Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences. The data may be used exclusively for non-commercial scientific research and must be stored and handled in accordance with strict confidentiality rules. Researchers should also note that access to the data may involve paying a data preparation fee (typically around €30).